

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

BORROWED WORDS AND THEIR USAGE DEGREE IN ENGLISH RIDDLES

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ABSTRACT

Riddles being one of the oldest and richest genres of folklore are valuable treasure of word reflecting the history, spiritual values, customs and traditions of the people in themselves.

Borrowed words in the English riddles are highlighted in the article.

The article determines riddles as short works the basis of which is a witty, metaphorical question that involves an answer. It should be noted that the vocabulary of the language is enriched in a number of ways and methods, in addition to internal capabilities. Words or borrowings from other languages in connection with this or that need are also accepted as one of them. If we pay attention to the examples of riddles in English we can come across words from different languages in the vocabulary of riddles in English. It is possible to come across words taken from mainly Celtic, Scandinavian, Latin, French, German, Italian and other languages in the English riddles.

Keywords: riddle, folklore, genre, borrowings, language, metaphorical, a genre of folk poetry, the vocabulary of riddles.

Introduction: Riddle is one of the oldest and most interesting genres of folk literature. Over the centuries, this genre has undergone various changes from generation to generation. Changing its form and content, gaining a new meaning and content riddles have survived to the present day.

Specificity of riddles is that in their concealed allegorical form an object or phenomenon is encrypted and one should find its original meaning. An efficient solving of riddles promotes understanding of their linguistic and semantic structure. Researchers mention that "any riddle is a kind of logical task because it contains evident or hidden form, a question that you need to answer".

The subject of this research is to reveal in details the using of borrowings in **English riddles**.

The Aim of the research: To understand more about the way English riddles are created.

Methods of the research: All the investigations are held with the help of investigation methods, and all the methods should be determined and chosen in connection with the topic investigated. In the investigation process of the given topic we have used the descriptive method and linguistic analysis method.

The theoretical and practical value of the research is that riddles are analysed from the point of view of the linguistic picture of the world reflection in their text.

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It is possible to come across words taken from mainly Celtic, Scandinavian, Latin, French, German, Italian and other languages in the English riddles.

Example:

The strangest creature you'll ever find:

Two eyes in front and many more behind.

The word "*creature*" used in this riddle is the word "*crēatūra*" from the ancient Latin church language, the origin of which is lat. *crēare* is related to the verb *to create*. The word "*front*" in the riddle is derived from the Latin "*frōns*" and is in the meaning of *forehead*.

Two brothers we are,
Great burdens we bear,
On which we are bitterly pressed;
The truth is to say,
We are full all the day,
And empty when we go to rest.

The word "*burden*" used in this riddle is derived from the ancient French word *bourdon*. The word "*press*" originated in the 14th century from the ancient French word *presser* and the latter from the Latin *pressāre*.

Clean, but not water,
White, but not snow,
Sweet, but not ice-cream, What is it? (Sugar)

The *cream*, the second side of the compound word "*ice-cream*" in the riddle, is related to the ancient French word "*cresme*", the early Latin word "*crāmum*" and is of Celtic origin.

What is always coming, but never arrives? (Tomorrow)

The word "*arrive*" in this riddle is related to the ancient French word "*ariver*", which means *to descend, to reach the shore*. Its development in English from the 13th century is mentioned in dictionaries.

I have not wings, yet I fly.

I have not eyes, yet I cry. What am I? (Cloud)

The word "*wing*" is of Scandinavian origin and has been used in English since the 12th century. Etymologically, it is associated with the ancient Scandinavian word "*vængir*".

I weaken all men for hours each day.

I show you strange visions while you are away.

I take you by night, by day take you back,

None suffer to have me, but do from my lack.

What am I? (Sleep)

The two words in the riddle - "*strange*" and "*suffer*" - are derived in origin. The development of both

lexical units in English from the 13th century is recorded in dictionaries. The word "*strange*" is etymologically related to the ancient French word "*estrange*", the Latin word "*extrāneus*" and is used to mean "*outside*". The word "*Suffer*" is related to the Latin word "*sufferre*" - *sub-* + *ferre* "*to bear*".

Surely all people
Who deserve to be here
Have visited a place where
All and Nothing Can be found. (Dictionary)

In the riddle, both the words "*deserve*" and "*visit*" are derived. The first word is of ancient French "*deservir*", Latin "*dēservīre*" origin. In Latin, "*de-* + *servīre*" means "*to serve*". The second word, "*visit*," is derived from the Latin word *vīsītāre*, which is etymologically related to the verbs "*vīsere*" to examine and "*vidēre*" to see .

A box without hinges, key, or lid,
Yet golden treasure inside is hid (An egg).

The word *treasure* used in the riddle is a borrowed word. The usage of this word in English dates back to the 12th century. The etymological connection of ancient French *tresor* with the Latin *thēsauros* is shown in dictionaries. These are also related to the word *thēsauros* in Greek. It means "*something reserved*".

Where can you find roads without cars, forests without trees and cities without houses? (On a map)
"*Forest*" in the riddle is a borrowed word. The transition to English dates back to the 13th century. The word was translated into English from Old French. It is associated with ancient French and medieval Latin word "*forestis*". It was used in the meaning of "*unfenced forest area, land*"

A warrior amongst the flowers, he bears a thrusting sword.

He uses it when'er he must to defend his golden hoard.

What is he? (A Bee)

Lexicographical sources date the development of the English word "*warrior*" in the riddle to the 13th century. This lexeme is connected with the word "*werreior* // *werreior*" in the ancient northern French language, the origin of which is connected with the name *guerreior*, derived from the ancient French verb *guerre* "*war*" - *guerreier* "*make war*".

In spring I am gay in handsome array;
in summer more clothing I wear;
when colder it grows I fling off my clothes;
and in winter quite naked appear.

What am I? (A Tree)

The use of the word "*appear*" in the riddle in English dates back to the 13th century. It is derived from the ancient French verb "*aparoir*". The source is the Latin verb *appārēre* .

The word *fling* in the riddle is also derived. The use of this word in English dates back to the 13th century. However, the source language for acquisition is Scandinavian.

In this riddle, the word *array*, which is included in English, belongs to medieval English. The source is the ancient French verb *arayer* (*to arrange*). The verb *aroi* (*arrangement*) is derived from this verb.

A time when they're green, a time when they're brown,

But both of these times, cause me to frown.

But just in between, for a very short while,
They're perfect and yellow, and cause me to smile!

What am I talking about here? (Bananas)

The verb to *frown* used in this riddle is derived from the ancient French verb *froigner*. Another source mentions that the word is of Celtic origin and it can be compared with the Welsh word "*froen*" and the medieval Breton word "*froan*".

Never resting, never still.
Moving silently from hill to hill.
It does not walk, run or trot,
All is cool where it is not.

What is it? (Sunshine)

The English origin of the word "*trot*" in the above riddle dates back to the 13th century - medieval English. It is believed that the word is derived from the ancient French verb "*troter*" (to flee) in the form "*trot*".

My life can be measured in hours,
I serve by being devoured.

Thin, I am quick

Fat, I am slow

Wind is my foe (A candle).

The word "*devour*" is derived from the ancient French word "*devourer*". The usage of this word in English dates back to the 14th century.

Conclusion

Paying attention to the riddles according to the origin of the vocabulary, as mentioned above, expands the history of long-term interactions of languages, changes in the lexical system of each language and their causes. Changes in the lexical system affect all aspects of the structure of language. The historical development of each level depends on specific conditions and reasons that stimulate changes in the lexical composition of the language.

The riddle employs quite ordinary language in conventional ways to satisfy the demands placed upon it as the art form; that is the reason why riddles conform to a model of communication which is made up of a code and an encoded message that is first transmitted and then decoded .

In the process of analyzing the borrowed words used in the language of English riddles, it can be concluded that the borrowings in English riddles are mostly of French, Latin (ancient Latin church language) and Scandinavian origin.

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